

TIBBİ VE AROMATİK BİTKİLERDEN EKSTRAKT ELDESİNDE KULLANILAN YÖNTEMLER VE TEKNOLOJİLERE GENEL BİR BAKIŞ

AN OVERVIEW OF THE METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES USED TO OBTAIN
EXTRACTS FROM MEDICINAL AND AROMATIC PLANTS

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ÖZET

Bitkisel tıbbi ürünlere, nutrasötiklere ve doğal ürünlere olan talebin tüm dünyada artmasıyla birlikte, yüksek kalitede ekstraktlar ve uçucu yağların üretimini mümkün kılan en uygun ekstraksiyon teknolojileri araştırılmaya devam etmektedir. Tıbbi bitkiler; geleneksel tıp ilaçları, modern ilaçlar, nutrasötikler, kozmesötikler, gıda takviyeleri ile farmasötik ara ürünlerin eldesi için gerekli kimyasal bileşikler bakımından zengin, biyolojik ilaç kaynaklarıdır. Aromatik bitkiler ise gıda ve kozmetik endüstrilerinde ihtiyaç duyulan kokulandırma veya tatlandırma işlemlerinde kullanılan terpenler veya fenolikler gibi bileşikler bakımından zengin bitkilerdir. Gelişmekte olan ülkelerde üretilen tıbbi ve aromatik bitkiler (TAB), gelişmiş ülkelere satın alındıktan sonra çeşitli endüstrilerde ihtiyaç duyulan ve daha yüksek ekonomik değeri olan hammadde veya ürünlere dönüştürülmektedirler. TAB biyokaynaklarında katma değer yaratmanın ilk adımı, basit geleneksel teknolojilerden gelişmiş ekstraksiyon tekniklerine kadar çeşitli yöntemler kullanarak bitkisel ilaç preparatlarının (yani ekstraktların) üretilmesidir. Başlangıç materyali olarak kullanılan bitki organı veya dokusu, ekstraksiyon için kullanılan solvent, kullanılan ekipman tipi ile kullanılan üretim yöntemi ve hammadde:ekstrakt oranı ekstraktın kalitesini etkileyen temel parametrelerdir. Uygun bitki materyalinin, ekstraksiyon teknolojisinin ve ekipmanının, ekstraksiyon yönteminin ve çözücünün kullanılması kaliteli bir ekstraktın üretilmesine yardımcı olmaktadır. TAB biyokaynaklarından en yüksek ekonomik gelirin elde edilebilmesi için ekstraksiyon teknolojilerindeki gelişmelerin ve üretimdeki kalite parametrelerine ait bilgilerin TAB çeşitliliği bakımından zengin ve gelişmekte olan ülkelere yaygınlaştırılması gerekmektedir. Bu derlemede TAB ekstraktlarının eldesinde benimsenen geleneksel yöntemlere ve en son teknolojilere yer verilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Aromatik bitki, bitki ekstraktları, bitkisel ilaç, ekstraksiyon, sekonder metabolit, tıbbi bitki

ABSTRACT

With the increasing demand for herbal medicinal products, nutraceuticals and natural products all over the world, research continues on the most appropriate extraction technologies that enable the production of high quality extracts and essential oils. Medicinal plants are the resources of biological drugs rich in chemical compounds necessary for the production of traditional medicine drugs, modern drugs, nutraceuticals, cosmeceuticals, food supplements and pharmaceutical intermediates. Aromatic plants, on the other hand, are plants rich in compounds such as terpenes or phenolics used in scenting or flavoring processes needed in the food and cosmetic industries. Medicinal and aromatic plants (MAP) produced in developing countries are converted into raw materials or products with higher economic value, which are needed in various industries after being purchased by developed countries. The initial step in value addition to MAP bioresources

traditional techniques to advanced extraction technologies. The plant organ or tissue used as the starting material, the solvent used for extraction, the type of equipment utilized, the production process followed and the raw material:extract ratio are the main parameters that affect the quality of the extract. The use of appropriate plant material, extraction technology and equipment, extraction method and solvent helps to produce a high-grade extract. In order to obtain the highest economic income from MAP bioresources, developments in extraction technologies and information on quality parameters in production should be disseminated in developing countries rich in MAPs diversity. In this review, the traditional methods and the latest technologies adopted in the production of MAP extracts were summarized.

Keywords: Aromatic plant, extraction, herbal drug, herbal extracts, medicinal plant, secondary metabolite

1. INTRODUCTION

Folk medicine started with the use of plant juices for the treatment of wounds and this practice was the beginning of the knowledge called traditional treatment methods. Early humans knew that plants had healing power. They chewed different organs and parts of plants such as flowers, fruits, seeds, stems, leaves, roots and barks to understand whether they were medicinal or poisonous from their taste and smell. Our ancient ancestors lived together in nature very well by observing the fauna and flora. For example, they have learned to overcome diseases by using the plants that animals use against certain diseases. They collected the plants that they discovered their medicinal value through trial-and-error and cultivated them also like the other important cultivated plants. They have obtained the first drugs by separating the active ingredients in the medicinal plants they have collected and produced throughout the ages with simple methods (Baytop, 1999; Sumner, 2000; Ronan, 2005).

Extraction, as the term is used pharmaceutically, involves the separation of medicinally active portions of plant or animal tissues from the inactive or inert components by using selective solvents in standard extraction procedures. The products so obtained from plants are relatively impure liquids, semisolids or powders intended only for oral or external use. These include classes of preparations known as decoctions, infusions, fluid extracts, tinctures, pillular (semisolid) extracts and powdered extracts. Such preparations popularly have been called galenicals, named after Galen, the second century Greek physician (Handa et al., 2008; Baydar, 2013).

A wide range of technologies is available for the extraction of active components and essential oils from medicinal and aromatic plants. The choice depends on the economic feasibility and suitability of the process to the particular situation. The various processes of production of medicinal plant extracts and essential oils are briefly overviewed in this paper.

2. DISTILLATION

Distillation is an effective separation and purification technique that has been used for a long time to obtain essential oils from plants. Distillation is based on the principle of boiling liquids with different boiling points together. Both liquids begin to boil at the same time and a temperature where the sum of the vapor pressures of the two liquids forming a mixture is equal to the external pressure. The boiling point of both liquids together is always lower than the boiling point of them separately.

Figure 1. View of Clevenger apparatus embedded on a round bottom flask and its parts (appareil de Clevenger Clipart images, 2021).

The distillation method that should be applied differs according to the characteristics of the essential oil contained in the aromatic material. In commercial essential oil production; water distillation, steam distillation, water and steam distillation methods are widely used. In all three distillation methods, essential oil and water are separated into phases in the collection vessel (fluorentine) where the distillate (distilled liquid) is collected.

The essential oils that are lighter than water accumulate in the upper phase, and those that are heavier than water accumulate in the lower phase. If a large amount of the essential oil remains in the water phase in the first distillation, only the oily water is distilled by going to the second distillation step called "cohobation" and thus all the essential oil is tried to be recovered (Fleisher et al., 1991).

2.1. Water Distillation

It is a suitable distillation method especially for dried or over-crushed aromatic materials and plants containing essential oil whose structure is not spoiled by boiling. In addition, water distillation is also used in the distillation of fresh plants parts. It is more economical and more practical than other distillation methods (Wang et al., 2006). Some disadvantages of water distillation are as follows;

1. Some esters are partially hydrolyzed and some aldehydes and acyclic monoterpenes partially polymerized due to the application of high heat and the decrease of pH value of water during boiling.
2. Some water-soluble phenols and alcoholic terpenes pass into the water phase, not the essential oil phase.
3. Distillation time is longer than others (Baydar, 2013).

2.2. Water and Steam Distillation

Water and steam distillation is mostly applied in the distillation of essential oils that degrade with heat and materials such as seeds, fruits, roots, rhizomes, bark that carry the essential oil in deep tissues. In this method, the aromatic material is placed on a perforated shelf placed just above the water level, the water is boiled and the hot and humid steam released is dragged into the material by passing through the perforated shelf. Thus, the plant material does not come into direct contact with the boiling water. If the material to be distilled is excessively moist, the passage of steam becomes difficult and the essential oil yield decreases. For this reason, the material to be distilled must be sufficiently dry and homogeneously fragmented. The essential

oil held by the water vapor condense in the cooler (condenser) and the essential oil layer is separated and accumulated in the separator (florentine) (Baydar, 2013).

Some important advantages of water and steam distillation method over water distillation are:

1. Essential oil yield is higher than water distillation.
2. The damage caused by hydrolysis and polymerization in essential oil molecules is also less.

However, distillation time is longer due to low vapor pressure (Seidel, 2006).

2.3. Steam Distillation

It is a method used in the distillation of aromatic drugs, usually consisted of fresh or dried leaves. It is mostly preferred in the distillation of aromatic plants that carry their essential oils on the leaf surface and whose essential oils are sensitive to heat (Boutekedjiret et al., 2003). In steam distillation, no water is put into the distillation boiler; The hot and saturated steam supplied from a steam generator outside the boiler is given to the plant material through a hose. In this way, the boiling of water is accelerated and the distillation time is shortened.

Figure 2. Steam distillation setup (Wasserdampfdestillation – Wikipedia, 2021).

Advantages of steam distillation over water distillation are as follows:

1. Since the temperature and pressure can be kept under control, the heat applied to the plant material should not be more than 100 °C. Thus, degradation of bioactive components due to high temperature is prevented.
2. Essential oil yield is higher than other distillation methods. In a study, it was determined that the distillation method has a great effect on the essential oil yield, and that 1.2% essential oil can be obtained by steam distillation and 0.4% by water distillation in rosemary. It has been observed that essential oil is obtained more quickly and effectively in steam distillation compared to water distillation, for example, while 80% of the essential oil is recovered within 10 minutes in steam distillation, 30 minutes are required in water distillation to gain the same amount of essential oil (Boutekedjiret et al., 2003).

3. SOLVENT EXTRACTION

The process of separating the active substances contained in the plants by selective solvents is called extraction. The product obtained as a result of extraction is called "extract". The type and variety of the plant used, the growing conditions and techniques, the solvent chosen and the

extraction method have important effects on the yield and quality of the extract. The points to be considered in the selection of the extraction process and method are given below.

1. Care should be taken in the preparation of drugs and in the collection and drying processes. Methods with high extract efficiency such as percolation and continuous hot extraction should be preferred in the extraction of crude drugs that are difficult and expensive to obtain and have low amount of active substance. Infusion and maceration methods should be chosen in the extraction of crude drugs that are easy to obtain, cheap and have a high amount of active substance.
2. Extraction should be done with solvents suitable for the polarity of phytochemicals, nonpolar solvents should be used for non-polar ones, and polar solvents should be used for polar ones. For example, nonpolar solvents (such as hexane, benzene, chloroform, ether, toluene) should be chosen for nonpolar molecules such as alkaloids and terpenoids, and polar solvents (such as water, methanol, ethanol) for polar molecules such as glycosides and phenols.
3. The solvent used in the extraction; It should be pure, should not dissolve in water, should not interact with the extract, should not explode, should have a low boiling point and viscosity, be easily separated from the extract, be recyclable, and finally be cheap and easily available.
4. Maceration, percolation and supercritical fluid extraction methods those require no or low-temperature must be adopted for the phytochemicals that are thermolabile whereas high-temperature extraction methods such as soxhlet and decoction must be preferred for thermostable phytochemicals. For example, for glycosides that are very sensitive to high temperatures, the extraction temperature should not exceed 45 °C.
5. Attention should be paid to the extraction time. If the extraction does not take long enough, bioactive substances cannot be separated sufficiently, and if it takes longer than necessary, unwanted substances (for example, tannins in herbal teas) increase. However, some bioactive substances (for example, hypericyrin, the primary active ingredient of St. John's Wort) are better recovered in long-term and high-temperature extractions.
6. After the extracts are obtained, they must be filtered to remove possible polluting particles and foreign materials. The filtered liquid extracts can be dried into powder by the method of spray drying (the device with a high-pressure pump system in which the temperature and flow can be adjusted in a controlled manner).
7. The bioactive substances of the product obtained as a result of the extraction should be analyzed by chromatography or spectrophotometry methods such as TLC, HPLC, GC, and the composition and amounts of the compounds should be determined (Baydar, 2013).

3.1. Extraction with Non-Polar Solvents

Anflorage and maceration are extraction methods with non-volatile oil solvents. If the process is done with cold oil, it is called "enfleurage", and when it is done with hot oil, it is called "maceration".

3.1.1. Enfleurage

Enfleurage is a method used to obtain essential oil when the amount of essential oil is low and accordingly other distillation and extraction methods are not suitable. In this method, the plant material is left in contact with an odorless, colorless, soft fixed oil mixture for a certain period of time. For this process (absorption), tallow or pure lard is mostly used (Baydar, 2013).

Figure 3. Enfleurage method (Un parfum à l'état synthétique peut produire une attirance., 2021).

Anflorage oil is prepared by mixing one unit of high purity tallow (bovine or sheep fat) and two units of lard. A case consisting of a glass plate which is placed between a two-piece wooden frame 50 cm long, 40 cm wide and 5 cm thick. Oil mixture is applied to both surfaces of the glass plate with a spatula. Enfleurage oils quickly absorb the odor by diffusion when contact with fragrant flowers. The oil must have a semi-solid surface. Thus, the flowers that leave their scent on the oil can be easily pulled out. Flowers are refreshed every 24 hours, depending on the species of flower. The process of removing old flowers with forceps and replacing them with fresh flowers is called "defleurage". Flowers laid on oil should not be overly moist or wet; otherwise the oil will oxidize quickly and become darker in color. After the oil reaches sufficient saturation, the glass plate between the case is removed and the oil on both surfaces is scraped with a spatula. After the scraped oil is melted, it is filled into a barrel and this final product is called pomade. Absolute is obtained by ethyl alcohol extraction of pomade (Colin, 2003).

3.1.2. Maceration

Flowers such as jasmine, lily and tuberosa, which can continue their physiological activities for up to 24 hours after collection, are very suitable for extracting their essential oils by the enfleurage method. However, the flowers of French rose, orange, violet and acacia cease their physiological activities immediately after collection. These flowers need to be distilled or extracted as soon as they are picked. In such cases, extraction with hot oil, that is, maceration, is applied instead of enfleurage (Handa et al., 2008). Oils to be used as absorbent in maceration (such as melted sheep and beef kidney fat, lard, tallow, olive oil, almond oil, paraffin and glycerine) should be colorless and odorless. 80 kg of absorbent oil is placed in a barrel and melted at 70- 80 °C. Up to 20 kg of fresh flowers are dipped in hot oil (45-60 °C) and removed after waiting for 1.5-2 hours. This process is repeated many times with fresh flowers until the oil is saturated with fragrance. At the end of each renewal process, the hot oil is passed through metal sieves and filter bags and is purified from flower residues. At the end of all renewals, 2-2.5 kg of fresh flower macerate per 1 kg of oil is obtained. The resulting scented oil is called "rose pomade" or "orange flower pomade". If desired, "pomade absolute" can be produced from these pomades by ethyl alcohol extraction as in the production of "enfleurage pomade". This process is continued until the oil is thoroughly saturated with aroma substances. Maceration is an inefficient process that takes a lot of time (Polat et al., 1997).

3.2. Extraction with Polar Solvents

Another solution to selectively take bioactive substances from raw drugs and to keep other unwanted substances away is using polar solvents such as dichloromethane, tetrahydrofuran, ethyl acetate, acetone, ethanol, methanol, acetic acid and water. The most commonly used solvent is water. For example, water is used when preparing herbal tea. Other commonly used

solvents are organic (carbon containing) chemicals, also called "organic solvents". They leave pure dissolved substances behind due to their low boiling points and therefore evaporation by distillation after extraction (Yrjönen, 2004).

According to the extraction technique applied and the nature of the solvent used, the products obtained are classified in different ways such as infusion, decoction, macerate, extract, tincture and pilul. Infusion, decoction, maceration, percolation, digestion, continuous extraction, aqueous alcoholic extraction with fermentation are widely used today.

3.2.1. Infusion and decoction

Water is used to isolate polar secondary metabolites from plant materials. Fresh or dry herbal drugs are kept in boiled hot water for a short time, then squeezed together with the residue, filtered and separated as "infusion". Infusion is a simple extraction method used especially in the preparation of herbal tea. The definition of decoction is boiling the drug with water together for a while (Handa et al., 2008).

3.2.2. Maceration

In maceration, water can be used as a solvent, as well as selective organic solvents. The dried and ground raw drug is kept in a suitable solvent for 3-7 days at room temperature and is mixed at regular intervals in order for the bioactive substances to dissolve better and pass into the solvent. The filtrate of the clear part accumulated on the residue and the filtrate obtained by squeezing the residue are collected in a container. After being filtered, the resulting macerate is stored in a dark glass bottle. The solubility of the solvent increases with the increase in temperature. Solvent is used 4-5 times as much as the raw drug selected for maceration. As the solvent:drug ratio increases, the extract yield increases up to a certain value (Handa et al., 2008).

3.2.3. Percolation

It is a widely used extraction method, especially in obtaining liquid extracts such as tinctures, which provides better recovery of active substances. For percolation, a cone-shaped container called a "percolator" that can be opened and closed at both ends is used. Before percolation, the ground drug is saturated with a suitable solvent (imbibition) for several hours. The drug dough, which has expanded by swelling, is filled into the percolator and enough solvent is added to cover it. The top cover of the percolator is closed and left for 24 hours. Then, the top cover of the percolator and the on-off tap are opened and the extract is poured into a container drop by drop. More liquid extract is collected by adding solvent from the top as needed. Unlike maceration, no concentrated extract is obtained by pressing the percolator residue (pulp). After the collected extracts are filtered, they are distilled in the evaporator under vacuum and removed from the solvent. To increase the extract yield, the solvent can be heated a little (with the increase in temperature, the solubility of the solvent increases and there is more transition from the solid phase to the liquid phase) (Baydar, 2013).

Figure 4. View of percolator setup (Perfume, 2021).

3.2.4. Continuous hot extraction

It is the process of continuously treating the solvent condensed in the condenser after evaporation in the Soxhlet apparatus with ground drug. The solvent placed in the glass flask placed on the heater is heated to the boiling point and the evaporated solvent is directed to the condenser of the Soxhlet apparatus. The solvent, which condenses and liquefies again, begins to flow in drops on the drug in the cartridge made of filter paper. When the solvent rises to the siphon level, together with the active substances it dissolves, all the liquid empties back into the balloon. The solvent, which starts to boil again in the balloon, is directed to the condenser purely (reflux), leaving the active substances it carries behind in the balloon.

In this way, the soluble active substances in the drug are collected in the balloon in each cycle by siphoning repeatedly. Finally, the solvent liquid extract (miscella) in the balloon is purified from the solvent under vacuum with the help of a rotary evaporator, and the dry extract is obtained. The solvent removed from the miscella by the evaporator is recovered by liquefying in the condenser. The Soxhlet method allows to obtain a high amount of extract with a small amount of solvent. However, since heat is applied continuously, its usability is limited in the separation of active substances that are sensitive to high temperatures. It is widely used especially in the extraction of fixed oil from oilseeds and fruits (Wang et al., 2006).

Figure 5. Soxhlet type extractor assembly.

4. HI-TECH EXTRACTION

Since the application principles can cover different methods such as distillation and extraction together, the methods used to obtain high-purity extract from medicinal and aromatic plant drugs by means of high-tech equipment should be included in a separate section.

4.1. Supercritical Fluid Extraction

In supercritical fluid extraction the gases that gain highly effective solvent properties under a certain pressure, especially in the supercritical phase, are used as solvent instead of typical liquid solvents. For this purpose, mostly carbon dioxide gas is used. Carbon dioxide is a non-polar gas, which has no explosion hazard and no toxic effect, is quite pure and can be obtained cheaply. The use of this method is rapidly spreading all over the world (Mukhopadhyay, 2000).

The efficiency of this extraction method depends on the pressure applied to the solvent, the temperature and the concentration of the solvent. Carbon dioxide is a non-polar solvent and its critical values are 31 °C, 74 bar (kg/cm³) and a density of 0.468 g/cm³ (Sihvonen et al., 1999). Under this temperature and pressure, gaseous carbon dioxide liquefies. These critical values of carbon dioxide can be further increased by using it with other solvents. The CO₂ sent from the liquid CO₂ tank to the extractor dissolves the phytochemical compounds effectively and quickly as it passes through the plant material and incorporates them. It is then diverted to the separator where it is reconverted to gas form by reducing the pressure below the supercritical level. This leaves behind an extremely pure and solvent-free extract. CO₂, which returns to gaseous form, is liquefied in the condenser and sent to the CO₂ tank (Vilegas et al., 1997).

CO₂ extraction is used in the production of antioxidant-rich herbal extracts as well as in the production of essential oils. Natural antioxidants may be degraded by physical and chemical damage while obtaining from plants with chemical solvents. Antioxidants from plant materials

can be obtained by supercritical CO₂ extraction method in a very efficient and pure manner without their structures being deteriorated and their activities reduced. The isolation of non-polar natural substances such as artemisinin from *Artemisia* plant, steroids from *Quercus* plant, azadirachtin from *Neem* tree, hypericin from *Hypericum* plant can be successfully done with CO₂ due to its nonpolar structure. CO₂ and polar solvents such as methanol, ethanol, dichloromethane and acetonitrile can be mixed in certain proportions for the extraction of polar substances (Baydar, 2013).

Figure 6. Schematic representation of the CO₂ extraction technique.

4.2. Ultrasound Extraction

It is an extraction method that enables the separation of bioactive substances from drugs by increasing the permeability of the cell walls and the resolving power of the solvent with sound frequencies of 20 kHz and above. It is a new method that has been effectively implemented in the separation of active substances, especially from some drugs (woody drugs such as coconut shell, grape seed) (Mason et al., 1996). Tartaric and malic acids from grape seeds can be effectively isolated in an ultrasonic bath at 24 kHz sound power, using water or aqueous methanol for 30 minutes at 70 °C (Colin, 2003).

The disadvantages of this extraction method are that it requires high facility costs in industrial-scale production, and that it can also cause unexpected changes in some bioactive molecules at sound frequencies above 20 kHz, and sometimes accelerate oxidation by causing the formation of free radicals. In order to avoid these disadvantages, programmable ultrasonic devices that apply sound frequencies by repeating them at short intervals have been developed in recent years (Romdhane et al., 2002).

Today it is used in oil, protein and enzyme extraction from oilseeds such as soybean and their press residue, in obtaining extracts rich in bioactive substances from spices and in obtaining better phenolic and color substances in fruit juice. In addition, ultrasonic assisted extraction methods are used in the sterilization of liquid food products such as milk, especially in order to minimize the negative effects of methods such as pasteurization with high heat and to neutralize microorganisms in food products (Baydar, 2013).

4.3. Microwave Extraction

Microwaves applied to the plant material directly enter the drug, vaporize the existing water molecules, and the resulting high pressure breaks the cells and ensures the release of bioactive molecules. The released molecules are then isolated by extraction with the help of solvents such as ethanol. By using it together with other extraction and distillation methods, extracts of higher

quality and efficiency can be obtained (Kaufmann et al., 2002). In comparisons with microwave assisted extraction, solvent extraction and steam distillation of medicinal and aromatic plants, it was observed that higher extract yield and higher extract quality were obtained from microwave assisted extraction. Especially, more extract can be obtained by using less solvent in a shorter time compared to other solvent extraction methods (Brachet et al., 2002).

4.3.1. Other Hi-Tech Extraction Methods and Combinations

There are some other high-tech extraction methods that use different principles and equipment from these technologies. However, most of these technologies (shown in Table 1) are often combined with each other including the methods previously explained in this paper.

Table 1. Definitions of other extraction techniques and methods (Fierascu et al., 2020).

ABBR.	TERM and DEFINITION
AFE	Accelerated Fluid Extraction Based on solvent with high pressure and temperature.
CAE	Cavitation Accelerated Extraction Based on occurring cavitation due to the passage of ultrasound waves in the liquid medium.
CCC	Counter-Current Chromatography Chromatographic techniques used for preparative isolation and purification of natural products.
CPC	Centrifugal Partition Chromatography Chromatographic techniques used for preparative isolation and purification of natural products.
EAAE	Enzyme Assisted Aqueous Extraction Extraction method enzyme assisted in aqueous medium.
EACP	Enzyme Assisted Cold Pressing Extraction method enzyme assisted, used especially for obtaining oils.
HVED	High Voltage Electric Discharge Non-conventional extracting method based on corona discharge, which through the control of voltage, can enhance heat and mass transfer; the process can be enhanced by pulsed high voltage electrical discharges in water or liquid medium.
ILMHDE	Ionic Liquid-Mediated Microwave-Assisted Hydrodistillation Concatenated Liquid-Liquid Extraction Extraction technique based on microwave concatenated with a liquid-liquid extraction installation, with two columns, which can separate essential oils (in the first separation column) and extract some components from the hydrosol (in the second separation column).
ILMSED	Ionic Liquid based Microwave Assisted Simultaneous Extraction and Distillation Microwave assisted simultaneous extraction and distillation, which use as solvents ionic liquids.
MASDE	Microwave Assisted Simultaneous Distillation Extraction Extraction method with two simultaneous processes, microwave assisted extraction and the distillation of essential oils.
OAHD	Ohmic Assisted Extraction Nonconventional extracting method that relies on ohmic heating by passing an electrical current through materials, instead of conductive heat transfer.
PEF	Pulsed Electric Field Extraction techniques that use short pulses of electricity (from μ s to ms) under high intensity electric fields (kV/cm), which leads to the formation of pores on the cell membranes with improving the extraction and diffusion processes, causing the permeabilization of the cell membrane.
PHWE	Pressurized Hot Water Extraction Techniques that perform the extraction under pressure, with water as a solvent.
PLE	Pressurized Liquid Extraction Extraction method that performs the extraction under pressure.
SFME	Solvent-Free Microwave Extraction Modified Clevenger-type equipment to obtain essential oils based on microwave.
SLE	Solid-Liquid Extraction

	A multi-step extraction technique, resulting in the release of the target product with or without disruption of the cells with a counter current operation.
UAE	Ultrasonic Assisted Extraction Extraction method based on repeated compression/expansion cycles caused by ultrasonic waves without the disruption of cell wall/membranes.
UAEE	Ultrasonic Assisted Enzymatic Extraction Extraction method based simultaneous on ultrasound and enzymatic treatment.
WEPO	Water Extraction and Particle Formation On-Line Extraction method that performs the extraction under pressure with a mixture of CO ₂ and ethanol or water and particles as a solvent with formation on-line.

5. MECHANICAL EXTRACTION

Although these extraction techniques are the oldest known techniques, they still maintain their validity and are already widely used.

5.1. Pression

It is an old method that can be used to obtain essential oils that decompose by heat treatment or that have a large amount of essential oil and can be easily obtained by cold pressing. It is frequently used to obtain essential oil from the fruit peels of Citrus (citrus) species by this method. Citrus oils are the most produced and cheapest oils in the world. The oils in the essential oil pockets in the fruit peels explode with compression and release their contents (Handa et al., 2008).

5.2. Incision and Tapping

Chemical substances such as resins, gums, pitches, tars, tannins, gums, balms, rubbers, waxy substances and essential oils can be obtained from the trunks of some silviculture forest trees by scratching. It is a frequently used method especially in the production of oleoresins (rosin and turpentine). Open wound and closed wound methods are applied in resin production from Scots pine tree (*Pinus sylvestris*). As a result of scratching, peeling and carving processes, the resins leaking from the holes drilled in the tree trunk are collected (Deniz, 2002).

Industrially, resin is produced from trees widely planted in the world by Mazek-Fialla and Acid-Paste methods. In the Mazek-Fialla method, cavities are opened with a mazek grater in the area opened on the tree trunk in dimensions of 40 x 40 cm and the bark part is peeled up to the resin canals, and 1-2 kg of raw resin is collected per tree from these cavities. In the production of resin with the Acid-Paste method, 40-60% sulfuric acid paste is also applied to the mechanically opened wounds.

In this method, a thin layer of acid-paste is applied between the wood and the bark in the reddened area of 40 x 10 cm opened on the tree trunk in March, and 3-3.5 kg of raw resin is obtained per tree with the spout and collection container. The production period is April-May or September-October, and the accumulated resin is collected by expanding the upper part of the wound by 2.5-3 cm every 10 days in these months. Acid-Paste method is faster, more economical, more efficient and less harmful to trees than Mazek-Fialla method. In Turkey, the Mazek-Fialla method was used before 1986, and the Acid-Paste method was used in the following years (Baydar, 2013).

6. CONCLUSION

Various methods are used to obtain raw materials that can be used in pharmaceutical and industrial fields from medicinal and aromatic plants and their drugs. In addition to extraction methods such as infusion and decoction, which have been used since ancient times, more

effective, efficient and less time-consuming extraction methods have begun to be discovered, especially with the development of technology, and these new methods are rapidly becoming widespread. All over the world, especially developing countries have been making larger investments in the cultivation of medicinal and aromatic plants in recent years in terms of economic returns. The fact that the active substance obtained can be used as a raw material in many industrial areas, despite its small amount, is the most important reason why many countries tend to invest in this area. In order to obtain bioactive components of higher quality and efficiency from medicinal plants, the cultivation of medicinal and aromatic plants, as well as research and development of current extraction methods, should be a very important goal.

7. REFERENCES

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